

Palacký University
Olomouc

 UCLouvain

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UNIVERSITY

The EU in the volatile Indo-Pacific region

EUVIP

Overview of Workshops Organized by the EUVIP Project

1. 1. 2023 – 31. 12. 2025

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Overview of the project

Project title	The EU in the volatile Indo-Pacific region
Project acronym	EUVIP
Project number	101079069
DOI	10.3030/101079069
Funding	HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme
Program	HORIZON.4.1 - Widening participation and spreading excellence HORIZON.4.1.2 - Twinning
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03
Website	www.euvip-project.com
Coordinator	Palacký University Olomouc (UP), ROR: 04qxnmv42 University of Helsinki (UH), ROR: 040af2s02
Partners	UCLouvain (UCL), ROR: 02495e989 University of Copenhagen, ROR: 035b05819 (until 2023-08-31) Lund University, ROR: 012a77v79 (from 2023-11-01)
Start date	2023-01-01
End date	2025-12-31
Project summary	<p>Through its concise training, research, communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities EUVIP will significantly contribute to shaping the new, rapidly developing academic field of Indo-Pacific Studies. The project will raise the awareness of the stakeholders (academia, civil society, politics, and broad public) of the strategic, political, and economic significance of the volatile Indo-Pacific region for Europe and for a values-based European approach towards this region. Together with its seven dissemination partners, the EUVIP consortium will create a sustainable European Indo-Pacific experts network and knowledge hub with strong dissemination channels to national and EU policymakers in order to strongly contribute to the EU's Indo-Pacific strategy and policies. In addition, EUVIP will establish a Myanmar Centre at Palacky University in Olomouc (Czech Republic) to connect academia with politics and the civil society. EUVIP will build on UP's strong expertise on Southeast Asia and China's Belt and Road Initiative, supplemented by the</p>

complementary expertise of three leading European research partners (University of Helsinki, University of Copenhagen, and Université Catholique de Louvain). To further improve UP's excellence capacity and resources, the three expert partners will provide training to UP's early career researchers, PhD students, and research management administrators. This transfer of knowledge will result in a much higher international visibility of UP academics through an increased number of publications in world-class journals, an increased number of Horizon 2020 project applications, an increased reputation and attractiveness of UP for renowned international scholars and students, and increased mobility and employability of the UP staff.

Overview of the workshops

Workshop goal

Transfer of knowledge – Strengthening of Indo-Pacific and EU competences and research skills of senior researchers, early career researchers, and PhD students

[Workshop 1](#): *PhD workshop: EUVIP Young Researchers' Group*

[Workshop 2](#): *New Security Dynamics in the Indo-Pacific*

[Workshop 3](#): *EUVIP-Research Day: Navigating Indo-Pacific Future Dynamics: What Implications for Regional Powers?*

Workshops list

[Workshop 4](#): *Perspectives and limits of the EU's values-based approach towards the Indo-Pacific: The interests of China, ASEAN, AUKUS and the Quad*

[Workshop 5](#): *EUVIP PhD Workshop*

[Workshop 6](#): *Myanmar workshop*

Related to

Project objective 1, Work package 2 (Task 2.4)

Workshop 1

PhD workshop: EUVIP Young Researchers' Group

6. 3. 2023

Zoom

Workshop summary:

The first PhD workshop took place in March 2023 at Palacký University Olomouc and spanned four full days. This workshop was not included in the original project proposal but was made possible through additional funding from Palacký University Olomouc. The lead researchers from each partner institution – University of Helsinki, University of Copenhagen, UCLouvain – were invited to Olomouc to deliver lectures on specific aspects of doctoral research in the Humanities and Social Sciences and to provide individual feedback to ten departmental PhD students.

In addition, the three consortium experts were paired with five Palacký University doctoral students and agreed to provide regular, structured feedback on their theses over the subsequent three years, both online and during in-person meetings at EUVIP events. Given the substantial benefits to the participating students and the contribution to consortium cohesion, the workshop format was repeated in November 2024.

Related materials:

- [Workshop webpage](#)

Workshop 2

New Security Dynamics in the Indo-Pacific

29. – 30. 5. 2023

University of Helsinki

Workshop summary:

The first research-oriented workshop, titled “New Security Dynamics in the Indo-Pacific,” was held at the University of Helsinki in May 2023 and lasted two days. The workshop brought together researchers from the EUVIP consortium, invited experts, early-career researchers, and PhD students. It provided a forum for comparative analysis of regional strategies in the Indo-Pacific, addressing themes such as connectivity, regional security dynamics – including the South China Sea dispute and multilateral alliances – and the China–US rivalry. The event also enabled consortium researchers to present and discuss work in progress, receiving structured feedback.

The workshop was led by the University of Helsinki and featured presentations by all consortium members, examining European engagement with the Indo-Pacific from multiple perspectives. Discussions addressed connectivity initiatives, prospects for EU–Indo-Pacific cooperation, and domestic political dynamics influencing foreign policy, including potential policy shifts under South Korea’s new president. The second day focused on the South China Sea dispute and the importance of upholding international law, as well as the EU’s role in regional security and opportunities for enhanced cooperation with India. The final panel, hosted by the Finnish Institute of International Affairs (FIIA), an EUVIP dissemination partner, and concentrated on the China–US rivalry, particularly technological competition, in the context of the AUKUS trilateral security pact.

Related materials:

- [Workshop webpage](#)
- [Workshop program](#)

Workshop 3

EUVIP-Research Day: Navigating Indo-Pacific Future Dynamics: What Implications for Regional Powers?

11. – 15. 9. 2023

Ottignies-Louvain-la-Neuve

Workshop summary:

The third workshop was organized by UCLouvain in Louvain in September 2023 and lasted five days. It commenced with the EUVIP Research Day entitled “Navigating Indo-Pacific Future Dynamics: What Implications for Regional Powers?” held on 11 September 2023 in Louvain-la-Neuve. The Research Day featured two panel sessions. Panel 1 examined how small and middle powers in the Indo-Pacific navigate a high-tension environment, with contributions from academics representing Nanyang Technological University Singapore, UCLouvain, and Palacký University Olomouc. Panel 2 addressed the past, present, and future of major power rivalry in the Indo-Pacific and its regional implications, with participation from scholars affiliated with UCLouvain, the University of Helsinki, and Université catholique de Lille.

Building on the Research Day, the EUVIP methodology workshop followed, designed for PhD students and early-career researchers (ECRs) to strengthen their understanding of innovative social science research methods. The workshop specifically addressed the needs of PhD students from the EUVIP consortium and UCLouvain and employed an interactive format in line with the Grant Agreement’s objective of fostering a stimulating learning environment. Its primary aim was to provide participants with a comprehensive overview of diverse methodological approaches in international relations and political science.

The program began with a session on mapping methods in the social sciences, offering an introductory overview of methodological approaches in international relations and political science research. A subsequent session focused on the practical aspects of political fieldwork, including ethical data collection. The first day concluded with a session on qualitative data collection methods. The second day concentrated on qualitative data analysis, providing interactive engagement with various analytical techniques. The third day addressed quantitative methods, introducing statistical tools commonly used in social science research, as well as mixed-methods approaches integrating qualitative and quantitative analysis. An open discussion session facilitated peer exchange and reflection on methodological experiences. The final day focused on research data management and ethics, covering best practices in data handling and ethical considerations to ensure responsible research conduct.

Related materials:

- [Workshop webpage](#) (EUVIP website)

- [Workshop webpage](#) (UCLouvain website)
- [Workshop program](#) (UCLouvain website)

Workshop 4

Perspectives and limits of the EU's values-based approach towards the Indo-Pacific: The interests of China, ASEAN, AUKUS and the Quad

18. – 20 3. 2024

Palacký University Olomouc

Workshop summary:

The fourth workshop, entitled “Perspectives and Limits of the EU’s Values-based Approach towards the Indo-Pacific: The Interests of China, ASEAN, AUKUS, and the Quad,” was hosted by Palacký University Olomouc in March 2024 and lasted three days. The first day was co-organized with the Czech Association of Contemporary Asian Studies to further expand the EUVIP network, reach a broader academic audience, and disseminate preliminary EUVIP findings to scholars working in the Czech Republic. The workshop was also listed as a regular academic course at the Department of Asian Studies at Palacký University Olomouc, enabling students to gain first-hand insights into current research on security-related issues in the Indo-Pacific.

The first day featured a presentation focusing on potential NATO cooperation with the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue. The day concluded with a lecture examining the European Union’s increasingly assertive advocacy of norms and values in its relations with the Indo-Pacific.

The second day opened with a panel on the EU’s values-based foreign policy. Members of the Palacký University EUVIP team presented on EU–ASEAN relations. Additional contributions examined the geopolitical versus values-based approaches of EU external action and reflected on geopolitical dynamics related to AUKUS. The second panel addressed perspectives on Euro–Indo-Pacific relations and strategic alliances, including discussions on the EU’s interest-driven policy towards India, the future of EU–India strategic engagement, and Czech foreign policy strategies towards China.

The third day was devoted to discussions on Sino-Western competition in the Indo-Pacific. Presentations analyzed Sino-Western rivalry in Sri Lanka and examined China’s broader strategic vision in the regional order.

Related materials:

- [Workshop webpage](#)

Workshop 5

EUVIP PhD Workshop

11. – 14. 11. 2024

Palacký University Olomouc

Workshop summary:

In November 2024, the EUVIP team organised a four-day workshop for PhD students focused on academic writing, publishing, and research data management. The programme combined thematic lectures, student presentations, and individual consultations with senior EUVIP researchers, providing expert feedback and directly supporting participants in achieving their research goals and advancing their doctoral projects.

The workshop opened with an introductory session, followed by lectures on research planning and organisation, publishing strategies for early-career researchers, and op-ed writing.

The second day included a session on writing a PhD thesis from a student's perspective, a meeting of the EUVIP Young Researchers' Group, and a lecture on data stewardship in qualitative research, addressing the management of interview data and the use of analytical software such as MAXQDA. PhD students also presented their research projects and received structured feedback.

The third and fourth days were dedicated primarily to individual consultations, offering tailored guidance aligned with participants' doctoral research. The workshop also included the opening of the Indo-Pacific Hub, accompanied by a panel discussion.

Related materials:

- [Workshop webpage](#)

Workshop 6

Myanmar workshop

12. – 15. 5. 2025

Lund University

Workshop summary:

From 12 to 15 May 2025, Lund University hosted an international workshop on Myanmar. The event brought together 30 participants, including representatives from EUVIP partner institutions, and included a dedicated one-day seminar for ten doctoral students from European universities.

The program featured keynote addresses and several book launches. In addition to these academic contributions, the workshop emphasised strategic research development. Sessions addressed joint funding applications, the presentation of the EUVIP project to a broader academic audience, and the exchange of best practices with a related Twinning programme.

Related materials:

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